

A detailed microscopic image of biological tissue, likely a cross-section of a plant stem or a similar structure. The image shows a central red structure, possibly a vascular bundle, surrounded by yellowish and blueish tissues. The background is filled with a dense, grid-like pattern of blue and yellow fibers, suggesting a complex cellular structure. The overall appearance is that of a highly organized biological system.

OMERO and ARC Workflow

User Guide

OMERO and ARC Metadata Transfer

- Investigation, study, assay excel files.
- Regions of Interest.
- Key-value pairs

OMERO and ARC Mapping

Project - Investigation, Study Metadata.
Dataset - Assay data & metadata.
Images - Image metadata to file rows.

OMERO

ARC

Recommended

ARC to OMERO

The icon consists of three overlapping green squares of varying shades, with a white letter 'X' centered on the top square.

X

ISA Metadata Files

- Login
- New ARC
- Open ARC
- Download ARC
- Explorer
- Commit
- DataHUB Sync
- History
- Validation

- Services
- Settings
- Toggle Sidebar

v0.0.54

/ home / niraj / Desktop / NFDI4BIOIMAGE
/ Tutorial / DemoPlantARC / DemoARC

Demo ARC with Image Data

DemoARC

Investigation Metadata

Identifier

DemoARC

Title

OMERO-ARC Demo

Description

Tutorial for OMERO and ARC integration. An ARC with Demo dataset.

Contacts

[Import Persons](#)

Investigation

File Edit Window Help

Display Groups ▾

Projects 1.

- root root
 - Project1 [1]
 - Project2 [0]
 - Project3 [0]
 - Orphaned Images

Screens

Attachments

Tags

Images

Administration

Search

OMERO.insight
Local Desktop Client

Import Data

OMERO Importer

Import Data: Universal

Select data to import and monitor imports.

Select Data to Import | Specify MetaData | Import #1 Import #2

/home/niraj/Desktop/NFDI4BIOIMAGE/Tutorial/DemoPlantARC/DemoARC/...

File or Folder	Owner	Project/Dat or Screen	Folder as Dataset	Size
Tree_Rings.jpg				
leaf.jpg				

Import Location - Select where to import your data.

Import For root root 3. **Select existing Project or add New**

Projects Screens

Project: ProjectPlant

Dataset: PlantDataset

Selection: Tree_Rings.jpg

Filter: All supported file types

4. 5.

Projects

- root root
 - Project1 [1]
 - Project2 [0]
 - Project3 [1]
 - ProjectPlant [1]
 - PlantDataset [2]**
 - leaf.jpg
 - Tree_Rings.jpg
 - Orphaned Images

Screens

Attachments

Tags

Images

Administration

Search

filter images

per row:

Workspace: 2 of 2 images

Acquisition Preview

General

Full Viewer

PlantDataset

Dataset ID: 102

Owner: root root

Dataset Details

Add Description

Creation Date: 2025-04-14 1

Tags (0)

Key-Value Pairs (0)

Attachments (0)

Ratings (0)

Comments (0)

Located in

OMERO Data History Mapr Figure Help Tag Search Minimal-Webapp Admin

system root root

Explore Tags Shares Add filter

root root

- Project1 1
- Project2
- Project3 1
- ProjectPlant 1
 - PlantDataset 2
 - leaf.jpg
 - Tree_Rings.jpg
- Orphaned Images

Name	Date	Size X	Size Y	Size Z	Size T
leaf.jpg	Mon, Apr 14, 2025, 01:40 PM	507	446	1	1
Tree_Rings.jpg	Mon, Apr 14, 2025, 01:40 PM	1796	162	1	1

PlantDataset

Dataset ID: 102
Owner: root root

Dataset Details

Add Description

Creation Date: 2025-04-14 13:40:47

Tags 0

Key-Value Pairs 0

Attachments 0

Comments 0

Ratings 0

Others 0

Zoom: [Slider]

1.

2.

OMERO WebClient
Runs on the web browser.

1.

3.

Info

Settings

ROIs [0]

Save Save to All Undo Redo Copy Paste

 Grayscale Histogram Interpolate

Min/Max

Full Range

Imported

User Settings:

root root

OMERO.iviewer

system root root

Explore Tags Shares

- root root
 - Project1
 - Project2
 - Project3 1
 - ProjectPlant 1** 1.
 - PlantDataset 2
 - leaf.jpg
 - Tree_Rings.jpg
 - Orphaned Images

Investigation & Study

```

DemoARC/
├── assays
│   └── PlantDataset
│       ├── dataset
│       │   ├── leaf.jpg
│       │   └── Tree_Rings.jpg
│       ├── isa.assay.xlsx
│       ├── isa.datamap.xlsx
│       ├── protocols
│       └── README.md
├── isa.investigation.xlsx
├── runs
├── studies
│   └── ProjectPlant
│       ├── isa.study.xlsx
│       ├── protocols
│       ├── README.md
│       └── resources
└── workflows
  
```

Local ARC

General Acquisition Preview

ProjectPlant

Project ID: 151
Owner: root root

Project Details

Add Description

Creation Date: 2025-04-14 13:40:47

Tags 0

Key-Value Pairs 0

Attachments 0

isa.investigation.xlsx (7.08 KB)

isa.study.xlsx (7.50 KB)

Comments 0

Ratings 0

Others 0

system root root

Explore Tags Shares Add filter

- root root
 - Project1 1
 - Project2
 - Project3 1
 - ProjectPlant 1
 - PlantDataset 2
 - leaf.jpg
 - Tree_Rings.jpg
 - Orphaned Images

Assay

```
DemoARC/  
├── assays  
│   ├── PlantDataset  
│   │   ├── dataset  
│   │   │   ├── leaf.jpg  
│   │   │   └── Tree_Rings.jpg  
│   │   ├── isa.assay.xlsx  
│   │   ├── isa.datamap.xlsx  
│   │   ├── protocols  
│   │   └── README.md  
│   ├── isa.investigation.xlsx  
│   ├── runs  
│   ├── studies  
│   │   └── ProjectPlant  
│   │       ├── isa.study.xlsx  
│   │       ├── protocols  
│   │       ├── README.md  
│   │       └── resources  
└── workflows
```

General Acquisition Preview

PlantDataset

Dataset ID: 102
Owner: root root Show all

Dataset Details

Add Description

Creation Date: 2025-04-14 13:40:47

Tags 0

Key-Value Pairs 1

Added by: root root

Key	Value
Microscopy	LM
SampleType	Leaf
Instrument	Zeiss LSM 880
Stain	Calcofluor White
ObjectiveMagnification	40x

Attachments 1

isa.assay.xlsx (6.98 KB)

Comments 0

Ratings 0

Others 0

analysis_scripts ▶

annotation_scripts ▶

export_scripts ▶

figure_scripts ▶

import_scripts ▶ **1.**

omero-arc ▶

util_scripts ▶

Upload Script

◀ back

ImageToCSV... **2.**

ISA Import...

Run ISA Metadata Import - Google Chrome

localhost:4080/webclient/script_ui/1557/?Project=151

ISA Metadata Import

Import metadata from an ISA Excel file attached as a FileAnnotation.

Object Type: * Project ▼

IDs: * 151

File OR

Annotation: * **Choose File** isa.investigation.xlsx

3.

4.

View Script Cancel Run Script

- Choose object type and ID.
- Choose Annotation ID or Choose from file the local machine.

General Acquisition Preview

Key-Value Pairs 4 **5. Refresh**

Add Key Add Value

ARC:ISA:ISA_INVESTIGATION:INVESTIGATION
 Added by: root root

Investigation Identifier	DemoARC
Investigation Title	OMERO-ARC Demo
Investigation Description	Tutorial for OMEMO and ARC integration. An ARC with Demo dataset.
Investigation Submission Date	
Investigation Public Release Date	

ARC:ISA:ISA_INVESTIGATION:INVESTIGATION CONTACTS
 Added by: root root

Investigation Person Last Name	Kandpal
Investigation Person First Name	Niraj
Investigation Person Mid Initials	
Investigation Person Email	nkandpa2@uni-koeln.de
Investigation Person Phone	
Investigation Person Fax	
Investigation Person Address	
Investigation Person Affiliation	University of Cologne
Investigation Person Roles	
Investigation Person Roles Term Accession Number	
Investigation Person Roles Term Source REF	
Comment[ORCID]	0009-0007-5101-4786

ARC:ISA:ISA_INVESTIGATION:INVESTIGATION PUBLICATIO
 Added by: root root

Investigation Publication PubMed ID	
Investigation Publication DOI	
Investigation Publication Author List	
Investigation Publication Title	
Investigation Publication Status	
Investigation Publication Status Term Accession Number	
Investigation Publication Status Term Source REF	

system root root

Filter Results 1 result

General Acquisition Preview

Search Advanced

Show search hints ?

Search: 0009-0007-5101-4786

Restrict by Field: ?

Name Description Annotations ?

Search for:

Images Datasets Projects
 Wells Plates Screens

Scope:

In group: All Groups v

Data owned by: root root v

Date: Import date v ?

-

Search

2.

Type	Name	Acquired	Imported	Group	Link
Folder	ProjectPlant		2025-04-14 13:40:47	system	Browse

3.

1.

Searching Keys and values

system root

Investigation 3

- Study1
 - Project1 2
 - Dataset1 3
 - bacteria-tracks.tif
 - beads.tif
 - Tcell.tif
 - Dataset2
- Study2
- Study3
- Study1 2
 - Assay1
 - Dataset1 3
 - bacteria-tracks.tif
 - beads.tif
 - Tcell.tif
 - Assay2

root root

Dataset1

Dataset ID: 51

Owner: root root

Creation Date: 2025-03-18 14:50:50

Tags 1

Assay1

Key-Value Pairs 0

Added on Project Project1

ASSAY	
Measurement Type	protein localization
Measurement Type Term	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/O_0008104
Measurement Type Term Accession Number	
Measurement Type Term Source REF	GO
Technology Type	Confocal Microscopy
Technology Type Term	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCIT_C17753
Technology Type Term Accession Number	
Technology Type Term Source REF	NCIT
Technology Platform	TCS-SPE confocal microscope DM5500Q (Leica Microsystems); LCS Lite 2.05 software (Leica Microsystems)
File Name	CLSM-stacks_latrunculinB/isa.assay.xlsx
ASSAY PERFORMERS	
Last Name	Schrader

Zoom:

Nested folders in OMERO can be addressed with tag sets and tags.

1. Create tag sets & tags inside
2. Add tags to project & datasets

OMERO to ARC

Key-Value Pairs

Text Editor root root

Explore Tags Shares

root root

- Project1 1
- Project2
- Project3 1
- ProjectPlant 1
 - PlantDataset 2
 - leaf.jpg
 - Tree_Rings.jpg
- Orphaned Images

Thumbnails

Add filter

3.

Zoom:

General Acquisition Preview

PlantDataset

Dataset ID: 102
Owner: root root Show all

Dataset Details

Add Description

Creation Date: 2025-04-14 13:40:47

Tags 1

Key-Value Pairs 3

Added by: root root

Key	Value
Microscopy	LM
SampleType	Leaf
Instrument	Zeiss LSM 880
Stain	Calcofluor White
ObjectiveMagnification	40x

ARC:ISA:ISA_ASSAY:ASSAY
Added by: root root

Assay Measurement Type	Light Microscopy
Assay Measurement Type Term Accession Number	https://bioregistry.io/NCIT:C17995
Assay Measurement Type Term Source REF	NCIT
Assay Technology Type	Microscopy
Assay Technology Type Term Accession Number	https://bioregistry.io/NCIT:C16853
Assay Technology Type Term Source REF	NCIT
Assay Technology Platform	Zeiss LSM 880

analysis_scripts ▶

annotation_scripts ▶

export_scripts 1. ▶

figure_scripts ▶

import_scripts ▶

omero-arc ▶

util_scripts ▶

Upload Script

back

Convert KeyVal namespace...

Export to csv...

Import from csv... 2.

Remove KeyVal...

Export to CSV

Exports in a CSV the Key-Value pairs, Tags, name and ID of the selected objects.

Check the guide for more information on parameters and errors:
https://omero-guides.readthedocs.io/en/latest/scripts/docs/annotation_scripts.html

Default namespace: openmicroscopy.org/omero/client/mapAnnotation
Authors: Christian Evenhuis, MIF, Tom Boissonnet
Contact: <https://forum.image.sc/tag/omero>
Version: 2.0.0

Data Type: Dataset

IDs: 102

Target Data Type: <selected>

Namespace(s) (blank for default):

Other parameters:

CSV separator: ,

Include parent container names:

Include Namespace:

Include Tags:

3.

View Script Cancel Run Script

Export to CSV
The CSV is attached to Dataset:2.

General Acquisition Preview

PlantDataset

Dataset ID: 102
Owner: root root Show all

Dataset Details

Add Description

Creation Date: 2025-04-14 13:40:47

Tags 0

Key-Value Pairs 1

Added by: root root

Key	Value
Microscopy	LM
SampleType	Leaf
Instrument	Zeiss LSM 880
Stain	Calcofluor White
ObjectiveMagnification	40x

Attachments 1

PlantDataset_metadata_out.csv (118 B)

Comments 0

Ratings 0

Others 0

4.

Click and Download

system root root

Explore Tags Shares

root root

- Project1 1
- Project2
- Project3 1
- ProjectPlant 1
 - PlantDataset 2
 - leaf.jpg
 - Tree_Rings.jpg
- Orphaned Images

Add filter

Thumbnails

General Position Preview

Full viewer Image ID: 103
Owner: root root

Show all

Image Details

Add Description

Import Date: 2025-04-14 13:40:49
Dimensions (XY): 507 x 446
Pixels Type: uint8
Pixels Size (XYZ) (µm): -
Z-sections/Timepoints: 1 x 1
Channels: Red, Green, Blue
ROI Count: 3

Tags 1

Key-Value Pairs 1

Added by: root root

Key	Value
RegionOfInterest	Whole leaf
ExposureTime	40 ms
SampleCondition	untreated

Added on Project ProjectPlant

Investigation Identifier	DemoARC
Investigation Title	OMERO-ARC Demo
Investigation Description	Tutorial for OMEMO and ARC integration. An ARC with Demo dataset.
Investigation Submission Date	
Investigation Public Release Date	

Added on Project ProjectPlant

Image Metadata to File

Image details & Key-values to file rows.

analysis_scripts ▶
annotation_scripts ▶
export_scripts ▶
figure_scripts ▶
import_scripts ▶ **1.**
omero-arc ▶
util_scripts ▶
Upload Script

◀ back **2.**
ImageToCSV...
ISA Import...

ImageToCSV.py

Export image metadata and key-value pairs to CSV, with download link.

Data Type: * Dataset ▼

IDs: *

3.

[View Script](#) [Cancel](#) [Run Script](#)

Activities

[Clear List](#)

 ImageToCSV
Click the file above to download.

4.

```
ImageName,PixelSizeX,PixelSizeY,PixelSizeZ,Channels,TimeAxis  
leaf.jpg,507,446,1,3,1,Whole leaf,40 ms,untreated  
Tree_Rings.jpg,1796,162,1,1,1,,,
```

Image Metadata to a File

Image details & Key-values to file rows.

Output csv file as ARC consumable.

A high-resolution microscopy image of a leaf cross-section, showing a dense network of cells. The image is color-coded, with different regions highlighted in various colors: a red square in the upper left, a green circle in the upper center, a blue outline in the lower left, a cyan outline in the lower center, and a purple line in the lower right. A central white box with a black border contains the text "OMERO to ARC". Below it, a smaller white box with a black border contains the text "Regions of Interest" in green. The background is dark, making the cellular structures stand out.

OMERO to ARC

Regions of Interest

1:1 200 %

1.

4.

2.

3.

5.

Info Settings ROIs [0]

Save Undo Redo Show Comments 2 Edit Delete

Comment 10

Z T

ROIs Planes

 Show Z T C Comment 1 1 1 1 1 1

/ home / niraj / Desktop / N4BI / Tutorial / DemoPlantARC
/ DemoARC

Login

New ARC

Open ARC

Download ARC

Explorer

Commit

DataHUB Sync

History

Validation

Services

Settings

Toggle Sidebar

v0.0.54

Markdown Editor

/home/niraj/Desktop/N4BI/Tutorial/DemoPlantARC/DemoARC/assays/PlantDataset/dataset/leaf.csv

```
ImageName,PixelSizeX,PixelSizeY,PixelSizeZ,Channels,TimeAxis,RegionOfInterest,ExposureTime,
SampleCondition
leaf.jpg,507,446,1,3,1,Whole leaf,40 ms,untreated
```


Metadata from OMERO to ARC

CSV files downloaded from OMERO.

Metadata folder added here.

Niraj Kandpal
git.nfdi4plants.org

New ARC 1.

Open ARC

Download ARC

Explorer

Commit 2.

DataHUB Sync 3.

History

Validation

Services

Settings

Toggle Sidebar

v0.0.54

/ home / niraj / Desktop / N4BI / Tutorial / DemoPlantARC
/ DemoARC

▼ DemoARC

- ▶ studies +
- ▶ assays +
- ▶ workflows
- ▶ runs

..lock.isa.investigation.xlsx#

DataHUB Sync

Synchronize the ARC with a DataHub

Remote

origin
https://git.nfdi4plants.org/NKandpal/DemoARC.git

+

4.

 Use Large File Storage

5.

Commit & Push to DataPlant DataHub

DemoARC

 Star 0
 Fork 0

 ▾

Find file

Edit ▾

Code ▾

Demo ARC

Niraj Kandpal authored 2 minutes ago

d1ecbe98

History

Name	Last commit	Last update
assays	Demo ARC	2 minutes ago
runs	Demo ARC	2 minutes ago
studies	Demo ARC	2 minutes ago
workflows	Demo ARC	2 minutes ago
.gitattributes	Demo ARC	2 minutes ago
~/.lock.isa.investigation.xlsx#	Demo ARC	2 minutes ago
isa.investigation.xlsx	Demo ARC	2 minutes ago

Project information
 passed
 Auto DevOps enabled

+ Add README

+ Add LICENSE

+ Add CHANGELOG

+ Add CONTRIBUTING

+ Add Kubernetes cluster

+ Add Wiki

+ Configure Integrations

Created on

August 19, 2025

ARC on DataPlant DataHUB

Project What's new

4

 Help

References

- Scripts : <https://github.com/Nirkan/OMERO-ARC-WebScripts>
- The Open Microscopy Environment. <https://www.openmicroscopy.org/>
- NFDI4Bioimage. <https://nfdi4bioimage.de/home/>
- DataPLANT. <https://www.nfdi4plants.org/>
- HHMI. <https://www.hhmi.org/beautifulbiology> . [CC BY-NC 4.0 license](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/)
- NFDI4Bioimage Wall Calendar 2024.
<https://nfdi4bioimage.de/resources-and-services/wall-calendar/2024-05/>

nkandpa2@uni-koeln.de